

THE ROLE OF AUDIO-VISUAL METHOD WHILE TEACHING ENGLISH IN THE SECONDARY SCHOOLS

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Annotation: *This article investigates the use of audio-visual aids in the EFL classes in secondary schools. Specifically, it aims to determine how audio-visual aids could work as an excellent motivational instrument for teachers and students in secondary schools.*

Key words: *Audio-Visual Aids, Teaching, TV, CD, films, videos*

Education is necessary for all. There is no doubt that, without education, no one can lead a good life. Teaching and learning are important elements of education. The teachers use different methods and materials to teach their students to make learning effective. Over time, different methods and techniques have been introduced in education. The teachers use different aids to make teaching effective. The teaching aids arouse learners' interest and help teachers elucidate concepts easily. There is no doubt that audio-visual aids are those educational aids used in the EFL classroom to encourage the learning process in teaching, make it easier and interesting. The material such as charts, maps, models, film strip, projectors, radio, television etc. is called instructional aids". "Audio-visual aids provide the learners with realistic experience, which captures their attention and helps understand the historical phenomena. They appeal to the mind through the visual-auditory senses. ". There is a famous proverb "one seeing is worth, a hundred words it is a fact that we receive knowledge through our senses. There is another proverb that if we hear, we forget if we see we remember, and if we do something, we know it"; therefore, it means that the use of audio-visual aids makes the teaching and learning process more operative. As Kishore aid "audio-visual aids stimulated thinking and understanding". The use of audio-visual aids in teaching and learning process has multifarious values". "The audio-visual aids provide opportunities for speakers to make a more professional and consistent presentation. The teaching profession is filled with countless opportunities to enrich students' academic life; while some educational concepts and goals will be easy for students to understand, others require you to think creatively to ensure important learning goals are achieved. "There are four kinds of audio-visual aids. They are films, television, video and CDs".

1) Films

Films represent an effective instructional device to cater to the students' attention and create interest and motivation among them towards practical learning. Educational films may be prepared on any content material or any aspect of knowledge and behaviour.

2) Television

Television is a versatile medium for transmitting education through different programs. It is an exciting means of communication. Useful instructional programs are being telecasted regularly for the student community on television. A teacher should utilize TV programs and make them the basis for discussions on relevant occasions.

3) Video

Video is a viable aid for effective learning and teaching. Teaching with the help of video is called video-aided instruction. In video-aided instruction, learners' comprehension is generally tested through a questionnaire, and video is an instructional medium that generates a much more significant amount of interest and enjoyment than the more traditional printed material

4) CDs

Nowadays, educational video-cassettes are easily available in the market. Educational CDs can be prepared on any aspect of the subject matter and curriculum. From the above, we can see that audio-visual resources are divided into audio visual and audio and visual resources and others with audio-visual resources that can either be in a projected or non-projected form.

The Advantages of Using Audio Visual Aids

There are so many advantages of using audio visual aids, such as:

1. Best motivators: They are the best motivators. Students work with more interest and zeal. They are more attentive.

2. Fundamental to verbal instructions: They help reduce verbalism, which is a significant weakness of the schools. They convey the same meaning as words mean. They give clear concepts and thus help to bring accuracy in learning.

3. Clear images: Clear images are formed when we see, hear, touch, taste and smell as our experiences are direct, concrete and more or less permanent. Learning through the senses becomes the most natural and consequently the easiest.

4. Vicarious Experience: Everyone agrees that the first-hand experience is the best type of educative experience, but such an experience cannot always be provided to the pupils, so in some situations, certain substitutes have to be provided. For this, we find a large number of inaccessible objects and

phenomenon. For example, all the Indian students cannot be shown the Taj Mahal. In all such cases, audio-visual aids provide us with the best substitutes.

5. Variety: Audio-Visual aids provide variety and provide different tools in the hands of the teacher.

6. Freedom: The use of audio-visual aids provides various occasions for the pupil to move about, talk, laugh and comment upon. Under such an atmosphere, the students work because they want to work and not because the teacher wants them to work.

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